

Dionaea muscipula (Venus Flytrap) Crude Extract as Growth Inhibitor for *Pseudomonas sp.* and *Staphylococcus sp.*

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Abstract

Antibiotic resistance is a worldwide health issue. Examples of bacteria that developed resistance are *Pseudomonas sp.* and *Staphylococcus sp.* which are common causes of nosocomial infections in the hospital, easily infecting immunocompromised people. With these bacteria now becoming more resistant, new antibiotics should be made. The researchers performed a crude extraction of *Dionaea muscipula* with 95% ethyl alcohol. The collected extract was then reduced to the following concentrations: 70%, 50%, and 30% to identify optimal solution. The Kirby-Bauer method was used for the antibiotic sensitivity testing. Results confirmed that the *Dionaea muscipula* extract is effective as an agent for the growth inhibition of *Pseudomonas sp.* and *Staphylococcus sp.* with 10mm to 39mm and 7 mm to 33mm average diameter respectively. Statistical analysis of the results using One-way ANOVA and the Tukey-Kramer test showed a significant difference between the zone of inhibition of the varying concentrations and when compared to the control antibiotics. The researchers also found that the plant, *Dionaea muscipula*, possesses possible antibiotic properties due to its plumbagin, phenolic acids, and flavonoids contents. Thus, *Dionaea muscipula* extract is effective as a potential antibiotic that can be converted into medicine in the near future with the help of further studies.

Keywords: *Antibacterial activity, phenolic acids, plumbagin, nosocomial infections, zone of inhibition, ethanol crude extraction.*

Suggested citation: Pineda, P.A.L., Pagarigan, J.L., Hernandez, J.P.M., Hundana, A.R.B., & Hilapo, D.C.G. (2025). *Dionaea muscipula* (Venus Flytrap) Crude Extract as Growth Inhibitor for *Pseudomonas sp.* and *Staphylococcus sp.* *European Journal of Ecology, Biology and Agriculture*, 2(2), 114-121. DOI: 10.59324/ejeba.2025.2(2).11

Introduction

Living organisms undergo series of changes to cope with the changes of their environment. Bacteria also undergo this complex process, thus the development of antibiotic resistance. Antibiotic resistance is the ability of bacteria to withstand the effects of antibiotics, making infections harder to eradicate. According to Castro (2018), the reasons for this resistance include the overuse of antibiotics, suboptimal dosing, and the wrong choice of medications due to inaccurate diagnoses. Due to this, the United Nations Environment Program (2023) warns that current antimicrobials are losing their effectiveness, leading to a rise in mortality. This can be supported by a study by Murray (2022) which reported 1.27 million deaths globally in 2019 due to resistant infections, which can possibly reach 10 million deaths by 2050 if not eradicated.

Among with these bacteria are *Pseudomonas* sp. and *Staphylococcus* sp.. Infections caused by these organisms are frequently isolated in hospitals, causing nosocomial infection (Belkacem, 2022), which worsens the crisis of antibiotic resistance. *Pseudomonas* spp., a gram-negative pathogen which affects over 51,000 people in the United States alone annually wherein 6,000 of it is due to its multi-drug-resistant strain. This bacterium is also known to be the cause of cystic fibrosis (Tom, 2020). Javiya (2008) stated that *Pseudomonas* sp. was found to be resistant towards multiple antibiotics, specifically penicillin, cephalosporins, fluoroquinolones, tetracyclines, and macrolides. On the other hand, *Staphylococcus* sp. is a gram-positive bacterium that was said to be the most common bacterium that was isolated from hospitals (Belkacem, 2022). The bacterium is resistant to the following antibiotics; penicillin, erythromycin, streptomycin, tetracyclines, and methicillin (Stryjewski & Corey, 2014). The choice of treatment for MRSA is vancomycin, in which the bacteria was also discovered to be resistant in 2002 (Chang, et.al., 2003).

To address the growing resistance, the researchers have recently discovered a possible new source of antibiotic, which is the *Dionaea muscipula*, more commonly known as the Venus Flytrap. According to Gaascht (2018), this plant contains plumbagin, a naturally occurring naphthoquinone which was proven to have antibiotic properties by Hsieh (2005). This also contains Phenolic acids and Flavonoids which according to Lobiuc (2023) possess antibiotic properties as well. Thus, arriving to the hypothesis that the Venus Flytrap may have the potential to be a new antibiotic source.

This study explores the potential of the Venus Flytrap as a new source of antibiotics by inhibiting the growth of *Pseudomonas* sp. and *Staphylococcus* sp., addressing the urgent need for innovative solutions to combat the antibiotic resistance crisis.

Materials and Methods

Ethanollic Crude Extraction

The 180-gram *Dionaea muscipula* sample was blended and ground into smaller particles. Plant was then macerated with 1.5 liters of 95% ethyl alcohol for 48 hours with occasional stirring. The mixture was then filtered through a filter paper and concentrated using a water bath at 60°C to obtain a semi-solid extract. The collected 10ml extract of the *Dionaea muscipula* was transferred to a 60ml wide-mouth amber vial and stored in a refrigerator at 2- 4°C.

Preparation of Bacterial Lawn

Nutrient Agar was utilized as base for bacterial lawn. Stock culture of isolated *Pseudomonas* sp. and *Staphylococcus* sp. were inoculated via aseptic technique with full streak.

Antibiotic Sensitivity Testing (Kirby-Bauer Method)

The growth inhibition sensitivity of the extract was evaluated using the Kirby-Bauer method. Six treatments with varying extract concentrations, along with two controls, a positive and a negative group

were prepared: the control group utilized erythromycin and cefuroxime. Treatment groups included 30%, 50%, and 70% extract concentrations, with a positive group at 100%. Bacterial plates were divided into two sections, with antibiotic discs containing either control antibiotics or the different extract concentrations placed on each section. The newly streaked agar plates with antibiotic discs were placed in a 37°C incubator for two days for bacterial growth. After incubation, the zones of inhibition were measured using a millimeter ruler to assess the extent of the antibacterial effect of each treatment.

Statistical Analysis

Frequency distribution table was utilized to collect and organize the results of the measurements in accordance with their varying concentrations. One-way ANOVA was used to identify the differences in the results. The Tukey test was used as a post-test to further explain and analyze the results from One-Way ANOVA. This helped the researchers identify the specific significant differences between groups.

Results and Discussion

To compare the significance of the plant extract’s inhibition properties, two existing antibiotics, cefuroxime and erythromycin, were used as control samples and were tested along with the extract treatments via antibiotic sensitivity testing (Kirby-Bauer method).

Antibiotic Sensitivity Testing (Kirby-Bauer Method)

Figure 1. Zone of Inhibition of the Different Treatments against *Staphylococcus sp.*
Source: Own Work.

Note: (A) Erythromycin (control); (B) Cefuroxime (control); (C) 30%; (D) 50%; (E) 70%; (F) 100% are the different treatments of extracts of the *Dionaea muscipula*.

Table 1. Antibacterial Activity of *Dionaea muscipula* extracts against *Staphylococcus sp.*

<i>Staphylococcus sp.</i>	100%	70%	50%	30%	Cefuroxime (Control)	Erythromycin (Control)
Replicate 1	23mm	15mm	20mm	21mm	11mm	25mm
Replicate 2	24mm	20mm	15mm	15mm	15mm	24mm
Replicate 3	30mm	20mm	33mm	15mm	7mm	22mm

Source: Own Work.

Table of the raw data and results of 6 treatments against *Staphylococcus sp.* showing the zones of inhibition exhibited along with Cefuroxime and Erythromycin for comparison.

The *Dionaea muscipula* extract showed visible results in inhibiting the growth of *Staphylococcus* sp. The antibiotic sensitivity test (Kirby-Bauer method) revealed that the extract formed zones of inhibition (ZOI) ranging from 7mm to 33mm (Table 1). Extract concentrations of 100%, 70%, and 50% showed no significant difference in antibacterial activity compared to erythromycin. As shown in Figure 1 the extract showed larger ZOIs compared to the control antibiotics erythromycin and cefuroxime. The extract showed great results in inhibiting the growth of *Staphylococcus* sp..

The results indicate that *Dionaea muscipula* extract is a viable antibiotic against *Staphylococcus* sp., comparable to existing antibiotics like erythromycin and cefuroxime. The antibacterial activity of the extract is likely due to its high content of phenolic compounds and flavonoids, which can disrupt bacterial cell membranes (Lobiuc et al., 2023). According to a study, flavonoids exhibit antibacterial activity by interacting with bacterial cell membranes. Their chemical structure, such as the number of hydroxyl groups and the presence of methoxy groups, influences this interaction. This study also demonstrated that flavonoids could inhibit the growth of *Staphylococcus* sp. (Lobiuc et al., 2023).

Statistical analysis revealed significant differences in inhibition among the extract concentrations and comparison to the control antibiotics. The p-value result of one-way ANOVA is 0.028269769 which is less than 0.05, indicating significant differences among the treatments. For the Tukey test, the effectiveness of the extract varied with concentration, highlighting the importance of dosage in determining antibacterial activity. Higher concentrations showed greater inhibition, but some lower concentrations also exhibited strong antibacterial properties, suggesting a complex relationship between extract concentration and antibacterial efficacy.

The response of bacteria to antibiotics depends on the concentration. High concentrations can exhibit bactericidal or bacteriostatic activity on vulnerable cells, while low concentrations may lead to bacterial resistance or other biological responses (Bernier, 2013). For instance, the 100% concentration of the extract showed a greater zone of inhibition (30 mm) compared to lower concentrations. A study conducted in 2008 found that lower concentrations of antibiotics can yield varied results, with some stimulating immune responses and others showing minimal effects against certain bacteria (Chopra & Linton, 2008).

The effectiveness of *Dionaea muscipula* extract as an antibiotic was assessed through the average zones of inhibition exhibited by each replicate. The extract proved effective against *Staphylococcus* sp., with zones of inhibition ranging from 7 mm to 33 mm. One-way ANOVA test results indicated significant difference between the effectiveness of the extract and the tested bacteria, demonstrating that all bacteria tested were susceptible. Therefore, the Venus flytrap shows a high potential source of antibiotic medicine for *Staphylococcus* sp.

Figure 2. Zone of Inhibition of the Different Treatments against *Staphylococcus aureus*

Source: Own Work.

Note: Erythromycin (control); (B) Cefuroxime (control); (C) 30%; (D) 50%; (E) 70%; (F)100% are the different treatments of extracts of the *Dionaea muscipula*

Table 2. Antibacterial Activity of *Dionaea muscipula* extracts against *Pseudomonas spp*

<i>Pseudomonas sp.</i>	100%	70%	50%	30%	Cefuroxime (Control)	Erythromycin (Control)
Replicate 1	25mm	29mm	39mm	15mm	25mm	45mm
Replicate 2	26mm	12mm	34mm	12mm	12mm	55mm
Replicate 3	29mm	23mm	20mm	10mm	23mm	40mm

Source: Own Work.

Table of the raw data and results of 6 treatments against *Pseudomonas spp.* showing the zones of inhibition exhibited along with Cefuroxime and Erythromycin for comparison.

Figure 2 and Table 2 presents the zone of inhibition (ZOI) produced by the extract at various concentrations in each replicates, alongside the ZOI produced by the control antibiotics. The extract demonstrated ZOI values ranging from 39 mm to 10 mm, indicating its effectiveness as an antibacterial agent against *Pseudomonas spp.*

This effectivity may be due to the main components of the *Dionea muscipula* crude extract which are plumbagin, phenolic acids, and flavonoids which are all proven to have antibiotic effects. In the study of Kawiak (2007) the mechanism of plumbagin is through the production of Reactive Oxygen Species (ROS) which bombards the cell wall of the bacteria causing oxidative stress and therefore apoptosis. Phenolic acids on the other hand, according to the study of Lobiuc (2023) act on gram-negative bacteria, such as the sample bacteria *Pseudomonas spp.*, by acting on the cytoplasmic level. The antibacterial property of phenolic acids depends on the concentration wherein higher concentration allows the phenolic acid to cross the cell membrane, thus disrupting the internal processes of the bacteria. And Flavonoids act by interacting with the cell membrane, but its mechanism depends on the structure of the flavonoids itself. All these could be acting upon the cell wall of the *Pseudomonas spp.* which is composed of an inner membrane, a thin cell wall, and an outer membrane with lipopolysaccharide (Tom, 2023).

Statistical analysis revealed significant differences in inhibition among the extract concentrations and in comparison, to the control antibiotics. A p-value of 0.000207137 which is below 0.05 indicates significant differences. The Tukey test shows significant differences amongst the concentrations of the extract as well as in comparison to the two control antibiotics, Cefuroxime and Erythromycin. The highest dose produced the largest ZOI and the lowest dose produced the smallest ZOI in each replicate. These measurements demonstrated significant differences, highlighting the importance of dose concentration in the extract's effectiveness against *Pseudomonas sp.*. This finding aligns with Bernier's (2013) study, which emphasized that bacterial responses to antibiotics depend on concentration. High concentrations of antibiotics may exhibit bactericidal or bacteriostatic effects on susceptible cells, while lower concentrations could provoke alternative biological responses, such as bacterial resistance.

It can also be supported by a study wherein it is stated that the effect of phenolic acids on gram-negative bacteria depends on the amount or the concentration of the said component and therefore may have contributed to the inhibition and the treatment/concentration played a role in strengthening the antibacterial activity of the extract (Lobiuc, et al., 2023)

Conclusion

The effectiveness of *Dionaea muscipula* shows that the extract is a potential antibiotic against *Pseudomonas sp.* and *Staphylococcus sp.* compared to Erythromycin and Cefuroxime as controls. The results demonstrated significant bacterial inhibition across all extract concentrations, with zones of inhibition ranging from 10mm to 39mm and 7 mm to 33 mm respectively. The varying doses of 100%, 70%, 50%,

and 30% showed that higher concentrations generally produced greater zones of inhibition. In addition, instances where lower doses exhibited larger zones of inhibition highlight its critical role in antibacterial activity.

These findings suggest that *Dionaea muscipula* extract is a potential antibiotic to combat drug-resistant bacteria. The study not only highlights the plant's potential for development into an antibiotic treatment but also addresses the pressing issue of antibiotic resistance. By offering insights into the plant's antibacterial properties, this research paves the way for further exploration of natural compounds as viable solutions to the escalating challenge of antibiotic resistance.

Acknowledgment

Researchers extend our gratitude to the faculty and laboratory staff of Olivarez College – College of Health Sciences Education for their cooperation throughout the study.

Conflict of interests

We declare that no conflict of interest occurred during and after the conduct of this research. It is also declared that this research is novel and unique and was conducted by the researchers first and foremost.

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